

COMMUNITIES

D2.4 Stakeholder Engagement Strategy in the Cleantech, Industry and Health CoPs

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EISMEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Technical references

Project Acronym	EIC COMMUNITIES
Project Title	Building Synergies and Communities around EIC Portfolios to raise the impact of the EIC deep tech research
Project Coordinator	Stefania De Santi APRE desanti@apre.it
Project Duration	September 2023 – February 2026 (30 months)
Deliverable No.	D2.4
Dissemination level*	PU - Public
Work Package	WP2 – Community and synergy building between EIC portfolios and projects
Task	T2.2 – Co-creation of CoPs community and synergy building activities
Lead beneficiary	4. EurA
Contributing beneficiary/ies	
Due date of deliverable	30 April 2024
Actual submission date	30 April 2024

* PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

v	Date	Beneficiary	Author
1.0	19/04/2024	EurA AG	João Amaral, Márcia Macieira
2.0	29/04/2024	EurA AG	João Amaral, Márcia Macieira, APRE, EBN, ICONS
3.0	30/04/2024	EurA AG	João Amaral, Tedora Aibu

Funded by
the European Union

1. Table of contents

1. Table of contents	3
List of Figures	4
List of Tables	5
1. Introduction	6
1.1 List of Abbreviations	6
1.2 Project overview and objectives of the report	6
2. State of the Art.....	8
2.1 About CoPs: concepts and development	8
2.2 Stakeholders – definition and engagement	10
3. Methodology	13
3.1 CoPs – Constitution and Formation	13
3.2 Criteria for Selecting Stakeholders.....	14
3.3 Community Building Sessions.....	15
3.4 Results - Community Building Sessions.....	17
3.4.1 Industry CoP	19
3.4.2 Cleantech CoP.....	26
3.4.3 Health CoP	32
3.4.4 Stakeholders.....	37
4. Engagement Strategy	42
4.1 Action Plan	43
4.1.1 Events.....	44
4.1.2 Communication.....	45
4.1.3 Action Plan for 2024	46
5. Conclusions	47
6. References	49
Annexes.....	50
Participation Guide	50

List of Figures

Figure 1 – Tentative list of EIC Communities Stakeholders belonging to the three CoPs and with transversal expertise.	14
Figure 2 – Total number of participants in the 3 workshops.	16
Figure 3 – Miro template covering the expectations, activities and topics to be covered by the CoP.	17
Figure 4 – Typology of Participants (Industry CoP).	19
Figure 5 – Type of Organisations represented.	19
Figure 6 – Countries of origin of the organisations represented.	20
Figure 7 – Expectations of the Industry CoP members.	20
Figure 8 – Type of activities that are relevant for the CoP members.	22
Figure 9 – Topics to be covered by the Industry CoP (according to the participants).	22
Figure 10 – Experience of participants with CoPs.	23
Figure 11 – Relevance of CoPs for the organisation development.	24
Figure 12 – Frequency of the CoP meetings.	24
Figure 13 – Stakeholders to be considered for the CoP.	25
Figure 14 – Typology of Participants (Cleantech CoP)	26
Figure 15 – Countries of origin of the organisations represented.	27
Figure 16 – Expectations of the Cleantech CoP members.	28
Figure 17 – Type of activities that are relevant for the CoP members (Cleantech).	29
Figure 18 – Topics to be covered by the Cleantech CoP (according to the participants)...	30
Figure 19 – Experience of participants with CoPs.	30
Figure 20 – Relevance of CoPs for the organisation development.	31
Figure 21 – Frequency of the CoP meetings.	31
Figure 22 – Stakeholders to be considered for the CoP.	31
Figure 23 – Typology of Participants (Health CoP).	32
Figure 24 – Countries of origin of the organisations represented.	32
Figure 25 – Expectations of the Health CoP members.	33
Figure 26 – Type of activities that are relevant for the CoP members.	34
Figure 27 – Topics to be covered by the Health CoP (according to the participants).	35
Figure 28 – Experience of participants with CoPs.	35
Figure 29 – Relevance of CoPs for the organisation development.	36
Figure 30 – Frequency of the CoP meetings.	36
Figure 31 – Stakeholders to be considered for the CoP.	36
Figure 32 – Total number of participants in all the sessions.	37
Figure 33 – Stakeholders per type of organisation.	38
Figure 34 – Stakeholders' country of origin.	38
Figure 35 – Expectations of all stakeholders.	39
Figure 36 – Type of activities highlighted by the Stakeholders.	40

List of Tables

Table 1 – Agenda of the Community Building Sessions	15
Table 2 – Stakeholders Engagement Strategy Indicators	42
Table 3 – Communication activities that target stakeholders	46

1. Introduction

1.1 List of Abbreviations

CoP – Community of Practice
DoA – Description of Action
EIC – European Innovation Council
EIC PMs – Programme Managers
EU – European Union
GA – Grant Agreement
NGOs – Non-Governmental Organisations
WP – Work Package

1.2 Project overview and objectives of the report

The EIC Communities project seeks to improve the visibility and impact of the European Innovation Council (EIC) portfolios through three thematic Communities of Practice (CoPs): Cleantech, Industry and Health. These CoPs, which include a pre-selected number of EIC projects and stakeholders under the relevant vertical, will foster interactions and synergies on an intra and cross-community level.

As part of the *Work Package (WP) 2 - Community and synergy building between EIC portfolios and projects*, this report aims to create an Engagement Strategy for the stakeholders that are and will be part of the CoPs in Cleantech, Industry and Health. CoP stakeholders must also reflect this diversity in gender, nationality, and cultural background, and no communication and community-building activities can be undertaken without accounting for the diversity of the engaged stakeholders.

The term “stakeholders” is used to describe all entities that are participants in the CoPs, such as investors, corporate representatives, SMEs, universities, research institutions, trade associations, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs), and regulatory and standard bodies. This excludes EIC projects and EIC staff members, such as Programme Managers¹.

¹ EIC Programme Managers are Carina Faber, Samira Nik, Isabel Obieta, Stela Tkatchova, Federica Zanca, Iordanis Arzimanoglou, Enric Claverol-Tinturé, Antonio Pantaleo, Francesco Matteucci, Franc Mouwen and Ivan Stefanic. Link: https://eic.ec.europa.eu/eic-communities/eic-programme-managers_en. Retrieved: 30.04.2024.

This report will show the profile of stakeholders that took part in the Community Building Sessions in each of the CoPs, that were delivered in M6 and M7 under task 2.2. *Co-creation of CoPs community and synergy building activities*. This report is also based on the *D2.1. CoPs: Governance structure and management*, and on the activities developed under and for the project by the consortium partners, as an example, the editorial strategy.

Furthermore, the results obtained in each Community Building Session and the activities to engage stakeholders will be presented.

It is important to note that the activities and strategy proposed in this report may be changed during the course of the project.

This deliverable was developed by EurA AG, in collaboration with APRE, EBN and ICONS.

2. State of the Art

2.1 About CoPs: concepts and development

The concept of CoP is well established, and the formation and development of CoPs in the academic and corporate circles has been a common practice since the end of the last century. What's more, if we think of CoPs in a broader sense, it is easy to realise that this type of group or community happens naturally and doesn't have a rigid structure. According to Wenger (1998), some CoPs are completely informal, made up of colleagues, members of the professional's close network or even other aspects of social life: “Communities of practice are everywhere. We all belong to a number of them — at work, at school, at home, in our hobbies. Some have a name; some don't.” (Wenger, 1998, p. 1).

Obviously, in the case of our project and this report, our focus is not on the development of informal knowledge-sharing networks, but on structured CoPs that have very clear purposes. Communities of Practice should have a formal structure (including a CoP manager) and activities that allow their members to develop their expertise and skills in a certain topic (Wenger, 1998). However, it should be noted that informality and flexibility in the organisation of CoPs, even those that are born with a clear purpose, is an inherent feature of their nature and operation, and must be considered when designing an engagement strategy for stakeholders. According to Wenger & Snyder (2020), Communities of Practice can be understood as groups of people who come together informally to address a particular topic that is important to them, sharing their expertise on it. Invariably, the primary outcome of any CoP is centred on knowledge, its sharing, discussion and, eventually, development, which does not invalidate the fact that some CoPs can be formed to address the development of specific tools or new approaches to particular challenges. Typically, CoPs were physical groups (usually from the same company or organisation) with onsite activities where participants came together to discuss a certain subject. Today, virtual CoPs (VCoPs) are also an important evolution of the traditional concept. This is the case of our project and the activities that will be delivered by the EIC Communities project. These virtual CoPs have the advantage of allowing for a continuous knowledge-exchange flow that goes beyond the physical limitations of traditional CoPs (Haas *et al*, 2020).

The literature about this topic - how CoPs are born and structured, how they are maintained and grow, and what kind of results they can produce - is very much centred on CoPs that develop in the professional environment and, more specifically, in the corporate sphere (Wenger, 1998; Wenger, McDermott & Snyder, 2002; Garfield, 2020). Something the different authors underline is the relevance that these informal communities can acquire within organisations and their more formal structures. Stan Garfield (2020) argues that the creation of CoPs is the most effective way of informing, sharing and debating different topics and challenges, as they enable more contributions to be received in less time than, for example, email, and are more comprehensive than 1-1 calls. In addition, CoPs are an excellent way to seek support from members who are interested in the same topic but who don't belong to the professionals' natural network of contacts.

CoPs may have different goals or formats, but they usually follow a common path in what concerns their development. As stated by Wenger, McDermott and Snyder (2002, p.68), "like other living things, communities are not born in their final state, but go through a natural cycle of birth, growth, and death." The studies of the authors on the topic allowed them to identify five different stages that each community will go through: potential, coalescing, maturing, stewardship, and transformation. A stakeholder engagement strategy is particularly important in the first two phases. Whilst this report doesn't intend to go into detail about the development phases of CoPs, it is worth noting that it is in these two phases that much of the longevity of a CoP depends on. Firstly, it is necessary to find common ground between participants and make them see the value of sharing experiences, stories and knowledge with others who are potentially experiencing the same problems or challenges; secondly, it is important to create opportunities and spaces for the members to get to know each other and explore common ground, realising the value they can derive from the community and what they can offer to other members. As a space for collaboration and voluntary participation, it is essential that in the early stages of its development, each community offers a site, a calendar with frequent events, and useful content to participants in order to achieve greater levels of self-management and autonomy in the following stages of development (Wenger, 1998; Wenger, McDermott & Snyder, 2002; Garfield, 2020).

Also, according to Stan Garfield (2020), a vital aspect of the development and sustainability of CoPs is the choice of the topic around which the CoP will be formed. Unlike teams or departments in companies, which are dependent on tasks to work properly, CoPs depend on topics that can aggregate and that have an easily identifiable terminology, rather than pre-conceived tasks to be carried out by their members. As Wenger points out (1998, p.1), “communities of practice develop around things that matter to people. As a result, their practices reflect the members’ own understanding of what is important. Even when a community’s actions conform to an external mandate, it is the community — not the mandate — that produces the practice. In this sense, communities of practice are self-organizing systems.”

2.2 Stakeholders – definition and engagement

The term stakeholder was introduced by Ackoff (1974) and developed by Freeman (1984) in the context of the development of the Stakeholder Theory, who argued that any group or person who may affect or be affected by the firm action should be considered a stakeholder. Dunham, Freeman, and Liedtka (2006) built up on this and established that any group or individual that is necessary for the existence of the company or organisation can be considered a stakeholder, namely customers, suppliers, workers, funders or members of the community in which the organisation operates. Some interpretations can be given to the term stakeholder, and different dimensions of analysis can be associated to the concept (Argandoña, 1998; Parmar *et al.*, 2010), but we will rely on Dunham, Freeman and Liedtka’s (2006) simpler understanding of stakeholder to develop this report. In this regard, within the scope of this report and the EIC Communities project, all representatives of organisations other than the EIC and the projects supported by the EIC will be considered as stakeholders.

Concerning how stakeholder *engagement* is understood in this report, the conclusions of Haas *et al.* (2020), who state that engagement is commonly understood as being related to the participation of stakeholders in the CoP activities, but it is also about their interaction with other CoP members, is a good starting point.

The success of a CoP depends very much on the engagement of its members. Regardless of the nature of its members (in our case, project or stakeholder), there is an important set of principles that, according to Wenger (1998), must be followed. The most relevant are:

- Choose an interesting topic to address in the community.
- Keeping the community active with regular events/activities.
- Achieving a critical mass of members [according to Wenger (1998) and Garfield (2020), a community should have at least 100 members].
- Encourage online discussions using a specific platform or tool.

The content to be addressed and developed within the CoP is also relevant. One of the most significant pieces of content for CoP members and, inherently, stakeholders, is the development of success stories, including direct testimonies from community members. For the sustainable development of the CoP, it is important to create success stories that have their origins in the community itself (Wenger, 1998), as a way of maintaining the engagement of its members and bringing new members into the CoP.

This is not an easy task, as virtual CoPs may face a lot of barriers or difficulties to succeed. There is a constant need to balance the time and effort that is demanded of the participants. Also, virtual CoPs tend to be wider in terms of the number of participants and their profiles, creating different expectations. According to Wenger, McDermott and Snyder (2002) and Schibi (2014), it is key to plan what the CoP focus is by identifying challenges, subjects or activities that are common to the CoP members, which is particularly important to manage expectations properly. This preparatory work should be agile and fast, as stakeholders need to perceive the value of the CoP very rapidly and will be expecting to access good content or meet interesting people without having to complete a lot of procedures.

On the other hand, these (virtual) CoPs are a continuous source of knowledge to all participants, even those who are not that active or participate in the activities adopting a more passive way (Garfield, 2020; Haas *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, successful CoPs may support innovation by promoting brainstorming activities or by keeping members updated on the latest developments of the topic covered by the CoP. As stated above, the success

of a CoP is very much measured by the levels of participation of its members. This will make the community attractive to other members, who will bring new expectations and challenges to the CoP. As argued by Wenger, McDermott and Snyder (2002), “when the community widens its boundaries, it risks diluting its focus. New members feel less ownership of the community’s topics, practices, and processes. When a community closes its boundaries, it risks suffocating itself. Most communities waver somewhere in the middle, with vacillating levels of activity.”

Summing up, in the relationship with stakeholders and in order to maintain their engagement with the CoPs, it is important to:

- know and manage their expectations for the CoP;
- deliver value quickly (trying to meet their expectations);
- promote regular activities that allow interaction and discussion between members.

3. Methodology

A qualitative-based methodology was adopted to collect data on the participants of the CoPs, namely their expectations and preferred activities. Three co-creation workshops (coined Community Building Sessions) were delivered between M6 and M7. Each workshop was dedicated to a single CoP (i.e. Industry, Cleantech and Health). The workshops were prepared in collaboration with the EIC Programme Managers (EIC PMs), who were responsible for disseminating the call and recruiting the EIC Projects for the CoPs and the workshops. The analysis of the results of these workshops followed the principles of qualitative data analysis: firstly, data was aggregated in categories; secondly, all the insights were mapped and charts were created; finally, conclusions were drawn based on this mapping.

This section describes the processes related to the workshops' preparation and data analysis.

3.1 CoPs – Constitution and Formation

The 1st workshop of the project that took place on 23rd October 2023 in Brussels, and was organised in collaboration with the EIC PMs and the consortium partners, was essential to establish the ground for the CoPs.

This workshop resulted in the reformulation of the topics of each CoP, the challenges, the projects and the stakeholders that should be part of it, as shown in the *D1.1 Needs assessment and the refinement of portfolio selection*.

Together with the EIC PMs, co-creative exercises were completed to support the identification and assessment of what would be the organisations and/or individuals participating in the CoPs. As a result of this, a stakeholders mapping matrix was developed to assess their relevance for each one of the CoPs: Cleantech, Industry or Health.

Inside these Macro areas, each EIC PM selected a topic to be developed under each CoP:

- **Cleantech:** Building Materials; Energy Storage; Novel Technologies for resilient agriculture; Emerging Cleantech; Co2 | N.
- **Industry:** Awareness & consciousness (in robotics) through Artificial Intelligence; Space debris sustainability/enabling space technologies; Sustainable materials & Manufacturing for Micro-nanoelectronics.
- **Health:** Neurotech.

After establishing the topics, the priority was to identify the EIC projects that would be invited to be part of the CoPs. This helped us to identify relevant stakeholders according to the profile of the EIC projects.

3.2 Criteria for Selecting Stakeholders

The first action to establish the CoPs was to go over the network of the consortium partners and create a list of potential stakeholders for this project. Figure 1 demonstrates the tentative target list that is in the Grant Agreement (GA). Given the consortium partners' network of contacts, this list will be kept as a valuable resource to bring new stakeholders for the CoPs. The second action of selecting the stakeholders involved the creation of a stakeholders

Figure 1 – Tentative list of EIC Communities Stakeholders belonging to the three CoPs and with transversal expertise.

mapping, taking into consideration the results of the first action, the project needs and additional contacts from the consortium partners network. Within the scope of the project,

150 stakeholders have been mapped. This map will be continually updated as more contacts will be added by the consortium partners.

The stakeholders mapping was developed with the contributions of all partners and took into consideration aspects such as base country, gender – respecting the good practices of building and promoting inclusive communities – the type of organisation or sector of activity.

Also, during the first co-creation workshop (M2) EIC PMs were asked to select potential stakeholders to be part of the EIC Communities project and the CoPs. In addition, an information session was organised by EBN targeted at EBN members to inform them about the project and opportunities for collaboration. The session gathered more than 60 EBN members and lasted for an hour.

Finally, to map stakeholders and better involve them in the CoP (and later publish them in the DEEPSYNC² platform), a survey has been elaborated giving evidence about the stakeholders typology, the field of action and interest, and the inclusivity issue.

3.3 Community Building Sessions

Three Community Building Sessions (co-creation workshops) were organised during February and March (the Industry CoP workshop was delivered on February 21, the Cleantech one on February 27 and the workshop for the Health CoP was delivered on March 13), with the following agenda (table 1):

Table 1 – Agenda of the Community Building Sessions

COMMUNITY BUILDING SESSION		
10:00 –10:05	Agenda for the day & Welcome words	Main Session
10:05 – 10:35	Individual presentation	Main Session
10:35 – 10:45	EIC Communities: brief presentation	Main Session
10:45 – 11:00	Q&A	Main Session

² <https://deepsync.eu/>.

11:00 – 11:30	Miro exercises	Breakout Rooms
11:30 - 11:40	Live polls	Main Session
11:40 - 12:00	Main conclusions / Discussion	Main Session
12:00 – 12:05	Closing remarks	Main Session

The main goals of these sessions were to introduce the CoPs to all participants and learn about their expectations towards it, as well as the activities they would like to see organised within the framework of the CoP. This last aspect (expectations and activities) was particularly relevant for the preparation of an Engagement Strategy directed to stakeholders, but also for the CoPs coordination. Overall, we had 140 participants³ in the 3 workshops, but only 94 participants had active participation during the co-creation exercises. Out of these 94 active participants, 10 were stakeholders (see figure 2).

Figure 2 – Total number of participants in the 3 workshops.

All the workshops followed the same structure, using the Zoom platform for presentations and discussions between participants. As support material for the conversation, the Miro platform⁴ was used, where all participants had the opportunity to actively contribute. The template used in Miro (figure 3) made it possible to address various issues and topics related to the CoPs development and the EIC Communities project. Moreover, in order to facilitate

³ Project and stakeholder representatives only. Considering the participation of EIC PMs, EIC POs and moderators, the total number of participants in the 3 sessions is 167.

⁴ Miro is a digital collaboration platform. More information here: <https://help.miro.com/hc/en-us/articles/360017730533-What-is-Miro>.

participants' involvement in the activity, prior to the session a participation guide was sent (Annex 1) to inform them in advance about the exercises that would be developed, the platforms to be used and the agenda for the event.

Also, a set of questions was launched using the Miro polls tool to collect some quantitative data.

Figure 3 – Miro template covering the expectations, activities and topics to be covered by the CoP.

In the next subsections, an overview of the expectations and activities of all participants in each CoP (including projects) will be provided. Also, details on stakeholders' expectations can be found in section 3.4.4.

3.4 Results - Community Building Sessions

To facilitate the analysis of the results from the Community Building Sessions, the data collected was condensed and categorised. This process was relevant to understand the

participants' expectations for the CoP and the activities that, in their view, would lead them to be more engaged with the community and its activities. These results are explored in this section.

As previously mentioned, with regard to the data on expectations and activities favoured by participants, we used a set of categories to make it easier to analyse the insights gathered:

- Business Support - support based on acceleration services directed to innovators (market research, business planning, product refinement and validation, fundraising support, etc.).
- Business Development - support in increasing sales, get new customers and reach to new markets.
- Fundraising – support in securing funding from public or private financiers and investors.
- Knowledge-sharing - actions or activities that allow a keynote speaker or a group of speakers to present and share their expertise or experiences. These speakers may or may not be CoP members.
- Matchmaking - networking-related activities. Can be of different nature. More targeted (eg: pitching events, corporate days, industrial fairs), or more open (knowledge-sharing sessions, round-tables).
- Mentoring – support provided by a coach on specific topics.
- Scientific Cooperation Activities – activities that promote technical cooperation between projects (this can be related to the application of technologies or development of common solutions).
- Strategic Design - under our context, these activities are related to the identification of common pain points in the organisations that are part of the CoP, as a starting point to co-create solutions that will help in the resolution of those bottlenecks.
- Tools and Guidelines - activities that generate tangible results, such as network platforms, guidebooks to support early innovators, and agreements to share data and knowledge. It is very related to the knowledge-sharing activities. However, while in typical knowledge-sharing events there is a passive attitude, this category is more

about creating/organising the knowledge that already exists in the group - a more active attitude.

3.4.1 Industry CoP

The Industry CoP Community Building Session was attended by 26 participants with an active role, including 7 stakeholders and 19 projects (see figure 4). The type of organisations present at the session varied considerably (figure 5), with representatives from university organisations or research centres being the most prevalent.

Figure 4 – Typology of Participants (Industry CoP).

Figure 5 – Type of Organisations represented.

Geographically, there is a trend for organisations from Central and Southern Europe to be more represented, with Belgium being the most represented country (figure 6). 24 organisations were represented (2 organisations had more than 1 participant in the session).

Figure 6 – Countries of origin of the organisations represented.

- Miro board exercises

In order to develop the CoP, manage members' expectations and correctly plan the community's activities, it was particularly important to understand what participants' expectations were. In the case of the Industry CoP, participants' expectations can be categorised into two main groups: knowledge-sharing and matchmaking (figure 7).

Figure 7 – Expectations of the Industry CoP members

Regarding the opinions gathered in the knowledge-sharing category, two main trends were identified: firstly, participants are interested in learning from the experience of other CoP members on how to increase/expand TRL levels or overcome the valley of death; second, there is an expectation that this CoP may help participants understand the EU ecosystem, including other projects, how the start-ups can be supported and what activities exist in the digital research field.

As far as the Matchmaking category is concerned, there is a clear expectation in the CoP that participation in it will make it possible to connect with other organisations with whom some kind of collaboration can be established (on product development or at a commercial level). This expectation is common to both projects and stakeholders.

On the activities that participants believe should be developed in this CoP to keep them connected and active (figure 8), three main groups emerge: matchmaking and knowledge-sharing activities (naturally, given the participants' expectations that can be seen in figure 7), but also activities related to the development of tools and guidelines. Matchmaking activities cover the introduction to organisations with the capacity to financially support innovators and opportunities to highlight the CoP participants, making them active players in the events (participants don't want to be listening to others only); on Knowledge-sharing, the activities that were mentioned were workshops, webinars or events on go-to-market strategies (from scientific project to an established company), on specific technologies or on how to increase the TRL.

Concerning the Tools and Guidelines category, this is very much related to materials or tools that can support the CoP members. In particular, participants mentioned a database with information about the participants and relevant external actors that can support the CoP, a map of the stakeholders/agents of the sector covered by the CoP or the development of a common space between CoP members to enhance the connection of the internal teams of each member (eg. internal communication teams); another tool that according to participants could be developed under the CoP would be a library of qualified parts (visual representation of what can the CoP members offer).

Figure 8 – Type of activities that are relevant for the CoP members.

Finally, all the participants were asked what topics/issues they would like to see covered by the CoP's activities - this point is particularly relevant to organise and support future project events. Invariably, most of the topics mentioned are very technical, being closely related to the cutting-edge technologies the projects work with. However, as can be seen in figure 9, it is possible to see that CoP members are also interested in topics related to the exploration of market opportunities and trends; moreover, there is a strong interest in the regulation of AI and its implications for the development of solutions and the businesses that depend on it.

Figure 9 – Topics to be covered by the Industry CoP (according to the participants).

- Zoom session polls

A set of straightforward questions were asked to all participants using the Zoom polls to complement what had been discussed in the miroboard. The questions shared were the following:

1. Do you already participate in any community?
2. Attending to your experience, how valuable the Communities of Practice are to support the development of your organisation?
3. In your opinion, what should be the frequency of our community meetings?
4. Besides our current group, what additional stakeholders would be important for you to have onboard?

The replies to these questions can be seen below (see figures 10, 11, 12 and 13). Overall, a high interest towards the CoP was identified, with 63% of the participants affirming that CoPs are a very important or indispensable for the development of their organisation and business; also, it was possible to identify the ideal frequency of meetings for this CoP, with 62% of participants saying that the CoP meetings should have a quarterly frequency (4 times a year) and identify what are the more relevant stakeholders to be onboarded in the CoP (65% replied that they want to see more start-ups/founders in the CoP).

1. Do you already participate in any community? (27 replies)

Figure 10 – Experience of participants with CoPs.

2. Attending to your experience, how valuable the Communities of Practice are to support the development of your organisation? (24 replies)

Figure 11 – Relevance of CoPs for the organisation development.

3. In your opinion, what should be the frequency of our community meetings? (26 replies)

Figure 12 – Frequency of the CoP meetings.

4. Besides our current group, what additional stakeholders would be important for you to have onboard? (26 replies)

Figure 13 – Stakeholders to be considered for the CoP.

3.4.2 Cleantech CoP

The Cleantech CoP Community Building Session was attended by 54 active participants (3 stakeholders and 51 projects). The type of organisations present at the session, similar to what happened with the Industry CoP, have a good diversity (figure 14), with a relevant representation from Universities and Research Centres, but also with a good presence of start-up representatives.

Figure 14 – Typology of Participants (Cleantech CoP)

Regarding the countries of origin of organisations represented in the session, we can find a broader representation of geographies compared to the other CoPs (Industry and Health) due to a larger number of participants. However, the trend of having a greater representation of countries from central and southern Europe continues, as we can observe in figure 15.

Figure 15 – Countries of origin of the organisations represented.

- **Miroboard Exercises**

In the Cleantech CoP, there is a clear expectation towards Matchmaking activities in the CoP, as we can observe in figure 16. The members of this community are mainly interested in networking activities related to events that connect them with complementary companies (to create additional value or provide technological solutions), B2B partners, and other projects. Developing a community with all these actors, where they are able to showcase their solutions and portfolio is something that is often referred to by participants.

Figure 16 – Expectations of the Cleantech CoP members.

Furthermore, two additional categories should also be referred: knowledge-sharing and business development. Comments under knowledge-sharing underline the interest in learning from others' experiences (eg: from science to market) and having a stage to share their own case. Moreover, they are interested in learning about best practices and being informed about the latest trends and other technologies. In the business development category, participants stressed their expectations in taking part of future EU projects, but also highlighted that having the opportunity to meet B2B partners/customers is key. From the comments of participants, particularly those actors representing start-ups or universities, there are bottlenecks in finding players that may have interest in the technologies that are being developed. Their expectation is to have the opportunity to be invited/participate in events that connect them with potential buyers/customers.

Naturally, due to the expectations that participants shared, matchmaking activities are those that would contribute more to keep the engagement of participants in the CoP (see figure 17). Particularly, projects are interested in connecting with other projects, piloting their technologies to potential buyers or having the opportunity to participate in portfolio events. Meeting experts in online events is also relevant for these innovators. Interestingly, participants of this CoP are also keen to take part in business support activities, namely workshops or webinars; the reference to IP is common but

communication and how to promote the technology and implement exploitation strategies are also important for projects.

Contrary to what happens with business support and matchmaking topics, under knowledge-sharing, participants are mostly interested in learning about the market, its trends and regulations. They are also interested in having the opportunity to share and listen to experiences from other projects that may provide valuable lessons and foster good discussions and collaborations.

Figure 17 – Type of activities that are relevant for the CoP members (Cleantech).

In a similar fashion to what happens in the other CoPs, the topics to be covered by the CoP activities and events (figure 18) are related to the technologies or sectors of each participant. However, compared to the other CoPs, the Cleantech CoP has an obvious interest in addressing issues related to the TRL journey (how to evolve) but also standards and regulations of the European market.

Figure 18 – Topics to be covered by the Cleantech CoP (according to the participants).

- Zoom session polls

Identically to what happened in the Industry Community Building Session (and the Health one), questions were asked to the participants to collect additional data (figures 19, 20, 21 and 22). Again, the vast majority of participants think that is relevant to participate in this type of community or group of interest. Also, members from the Cleantech CoP are aligned with their colleagues from the Industry CoP, and agree that regular CoP meetings should have a quarterly frequency. However, the Cleantech CoP participants would like to see more investors and policymakers onboarded, which is aligned with their expectations of increasing their business development indicators and learning how to achieve higher TRL levels.

1. Do you already participate in any community? (49 replies)

Figure 19 – Experience of participants with CoPs.

2. Attending to your experience, how valuable the Communities of Practice are to support the development of your organisation? (51 replies)

Figure 20 – Relevance of CoPs for the organisation development.

3. In your opinion, what should be the frequency of our community meetings? (53 replies)

Figure 21 – Frequency of the CoP meetings.

4. Besides our current group, what additional stakeholders would be important for you to have onboard? (51 replies)

Figure 22 – Stakeholders to be considered for the CoP.

3.4.3 Health CoP

21 participants were present in the session for the Health CoP, but only 14 participants (all projects) had an active role and shared their thoughts during the session. Due to the smaller number of participants, there was not a great diversity of organisations in this CoP and in this session: only start-ups and representatives from universities or research centres participated actively in the session (figure 23).

Figure 23 – Typology of Participants (Health CoP).

In terms of geographical representation in this CoP, there is an interesting balance in this CoP, since there is no country that stands out in terms of representation as there is in the other CoPs. However, in terms of regions, it is clear that Central Europe is very well represented at the expense of other regions (figure 24).

Figure 24 – Countries of origin of the organisations represented.

- Miroboard Exercises

The participants in the Community Building Session of the Health CoP, in line with the other CoPs, have expectations related to the Matchmaking and Knowledge-sharing categories (figure 25). On what concerns Matchmaking activities, participants (all projects) have two main expectations - finding partners for future projects/proposals and participating in activities or events that allow them to showcase their technologies and learn about other projects' solutions. Under the knowledge-sharing replies, participants are mainly interested in learning from other projects experiences and to have the opportunity to share their own experiences and learnings (similar to what happens in the Industry and Cleantech CoPs).

Figure 25 – Expectations of the Health CoP members.

Following on from these expectations of the members of this CoP, the activities that participants favour are related to the Knowledge-sharing category (figure 26). Examples of knowledge-sharing activities that would interest participants are: webinars or workshops that cover the state-of-the-art technologies in Health; events and activities on medical regulations pathways (it was pointed out by one participant as a major weakness compared to the US market); meetings to learn about other projects technologies and solutions. Health CoP members, contrary to what happens in other CoPs, are mostly

interested in participating in knowledge-sharing activities, and that should be the main driver for this CoP according to these results.

Figure 26 – Type of activities that are relevant for the CoP members.

If we discard the usual Technical Topics response to the question of which subjects should be covered by the CoP, it is possible to see that the members of the Health CoP are particularly interested in one topic, related to Artificial Intelligence and its regulation and ethics (as is the case with the Industry CoP). However, there are a variety of other topics that are also relevant and that were mentioned by the participants, namely: business development, market trends, standards and regulations and how to evolve the TRL level (figure 27).

Figure 27 – Topics to be covered by the Health CoP (according to the participants).

- Zoom session polls

The Health CoP participants are aligned with the other CoPs in terms of the frequency of the meetings (quarterly meetings). As it happens in the Cleantech CoP, participants would like to welcome to the CoP investors and policymakers. In common with the others CoPs, participants in the health CoP also feel that taking part in the CoP is beneficial for the development of their own organisations. Please see figures 28, 29, 30 and 31.

1. Do you already participate in any community? (12 replies)

Figure 28 – Experience of participants with CoPs.

2. Attending to your experience, how valuable the Communities of Practice are to support the development of your organisation? (15 replies)

Figure 29 – Relevance of CoPs for the organisation development.

3. In your opinion, what should be the frequency of our community meetings? (14 replies)

Figure 30 – Frequency of the CoP meetings.

4. Besides our current group, what additional stakeholders would be important for you to have onboard? (14 replies)

Figure 31 – Stakeholders to be considered for the CoP.

3.4.4 Stakeholders

In this section, the opinions of stakeholders who took part in the Community Building Sessions will be analysed. In total, 14 stakeholders attended the sessions⁵, but only 10 actively participated in the sessions (figure 32). To make it easier to read the results, we have aggregated the stakeholders who took part in the 3 workshops in a single analysis group.

Figure 32 – Total number of participants in all the sessions.

The stakeholders who took part are mostly technology parks or consultancy companies (figure 33). Logically, all the stakeholders work with entrepreneurs, researchers and start-ups on a regular basis.

⁵ The goal was to have 30 stakeholders taking part in the Community Building Sessions. In order to facilitate the initial development of the CoP, greater priority was given to the presence of EIC projects rather than stakeholders, which led to the participation of only 14 stakeholders. This change of approach to the initial plan was agreed by all the members of the consortium and the PO.

Figure 33 – Stakeholders per type of organisation.

As seen in the previous sections, the geographical diversity of all the participants in the community building sessions is limited. The same happens with the stakeholder representation (figure 34), with France being the most represented country. The other countries represented are Italy, Spain, Luxembourg and Belgium.

Figure 34 – Stakeholders' country of origin.

Another aspect that is important to emphasise, given the project's general objective of promoting good practices related to gender equality, including in the constitution of CoPs, is the fact that the majority of stakeholder representatives who actively participated in the activities were women (7 women and 3 men). If we consider the

sample of 14 stakeholders (all the stakeholders who attended the sessions, even if they didn't actively contribute), we can find a similar trend (10 women and 4 men).

- Miroboard exercises

The expectations of the participating stakeholders are very much in line with the general interests of each CoP, with three categories standing out: Matchmaking, Knowledge-sharing and Business Development (figure 35).

Figure 35 – Expectations of all stakeholders.

The main motivation of stakeholders to participate in the CoP is related to developing a network of relevant actors to promote their support services and identify synergies and trends in those sectors they work and have expertise in. Besides, stakeholders expect to meet partners from the ecosystem for future collaborations.

However, stakeholders also have a set of expectations that we have grouped under the category of knowledge sharing. In particular, stakeholders are interested in understanding the EU ecosystem and share/get learning from other participants while having the opportunity to have an active intervention in the CoP. Also, there is an interest in learning about future EU projects and calls.

Being highly business-oriented organisations, there are a number of expectations related to Business Development, particularly the participation in future projects and prospecting for new partners to develop proposals.

During the Community Building Session, stakeholders contributed with their own opinions on what activities would enhance their engagement and would be relevant for their organisations. There is not a clear type of activity that stands out (figure 36).

Figure 36 – Type of activities highlighted by the Stakeholders.

Curiously, stakeholders emphasised their interest in developing materials within the scope of the CoP. In particular, it was mentioned that it would be interesting to create tools to help potential start-ups’ clients or investors understand the new solutions or technologies being developed. Another suggestion was creating a visually attractive tool to showcase what each member of the CoP needs or can offer.

Logically, activities related to matchmaking (networking events with prominent players in the ecosystem) or knowledge-sharing (very focused on the European innovation ecosystem and its opportunities) are also mentioned by stakeholders as factors to keep their long-term interest in the CoP.

Finally, stakeholders were also given the opportunity to name the topics they would like to see covered and, unsurprisingly, the most mentioned subject was market opportunities and new trends (figure 37).

Figure 37: Topics of interest for the stakeholders.

The next section covers the set of actions that will be delivered to maintain a high level of interest and engagement of stakeholders towards the CoPs. These actions and activities will be tailored to match the expectations of stakeholders (and projects) and cover some of the topics that were highlighted during the Community Building Sessions.

4. Engagement Strategy

The Stakeholder Engagement Strategy presented here brings together the set of activities that will be developed with the goal of keeping the CoPs' stakeholders involved in the activities that will be developed and engaged in the discussions and exchanges of knowledge with other members of the different CoPs.

- Success Indicators

This strategy is not final and will be adapted, refined and applied to each CoP by the designated CoP manager throughout the project. In order to achieve the objective announced above, it is necessary to have indicators that monitor the level of success of this strategy. Thus, two indicators can be monitored:

- 1) the number of participations in CoP activities by the stakeholders' representatives;
- 2) the number of stakeholder surveys submitted.

While the first indicator directly covers the actual engagement of the stakeholders, the second indicator is more demonstrative of the interest and ownership they have towards the CoP. For this strategy, a stakeholder will be considered to be actively involved in the CoP if they 1) participate in two events of the project, and 2) submit the stakeholders survey confirming their interest in being featured on the DEEPSYNC platform.

Table 2 – Stakeholders Engagement Strategy Indicators

KPI	TARGET
Participation in Events	Participation in 2 events
Number of replies to the Stakeholders survey	50

This stakeholder engagement strategy was based on the insights gained from the EIC PMs during Task's 1.1 co-creation workshop, the Communities Building Sessions that this report explores, the experience that the consortium members have in animating this

type of communities and the deliverables that were prepared by the consortium for the development of the CoPs (d2.1 - CoPs Governance structure and management) and the implementation of communication actions (WP3).

- Key Success Factors

In order to achieve the objective of keeping stakeholders engaged and connected to the project, it is necessary to identify a set of critical factors that have been taken into account in the development of this strategy and the activities that make it up. These critical success factors are:

- Choosing a topic that is interesting to community members.
- Keeping the community active with frequent events or activities.
- Building a quality group that is large enough to guarantee the sustainability and interest of the CoP.
- Implementing activities that correspond to the interests of the stakeholders (namely actions that allow them to learn more about the European innovation ecosystem and its opportunities, and that allow them to connect with partners for future projects and proposals).

The matchmaking activities should then be directed to support these actors in finding partners that may help them leverage their business development. This is particularly important for these stakeholders, as these are organisations that work directly with start-ups. Also, for stakeholders, it is very important to realise which other organisations are taking part in the CoP, in addition to the topics that are going to be dealt with.

4.1 Action Plan

This strategy is based on the lessons learnt from the activities already carried out, is developed around two main dimensions: on the one hand, the preparation and implementation of regular events of interest to stakeholders; on the other, the

implementation of communication actions (figure 38). Both dimensions must support and reinforce each other.

Type of Events	Communication Actions
6 portfolio days	5 Newsletters
2 pitching sessions	5 Press Releases
2 Information Days	15 Success Stories
6 online thematic workshops / webinars	

Figure 38: Engagement strategy dimensions and actions.

Each CoP will have a professional responsible for its management, and the way in which each CoP is managed and animated may differ from CoP to CoP. All events directed to stakeholders will be online, in order to facilitate their participation, saving them resources and time. Also, stakeholders may learn about EIC projects and other stakeholders participating in the CoPs by accessing the DEEPSYNC webpage. Moreover, efforts will be made to explain and clarify the CoP activities and the EIC Communities project to new stakeholders that will be onboarded during the project.

Below, the actions that will be implemented to guarantee stakeholder engagement are clarified:

4.1.1 Events

- 6 Portfolio days (2 per CoP) will be delivered during the project. Each Portfolio Day will accommodate a minimum of 15 stakeholders per session, and will give the possibility to reflect on and discuss technological developments and policies

related to the topics of each CoP. they will have the opportunity to deepen the knowledge of the technologies and solutions developed by the projects, meet founders and other stakeholders.

- 2 e-pitching sessions per CoP will allow an active interaction between EIC projects and stakeholders, as they will have the opportunity to know about them and ask questions.
- 2 Information days focused on exploring forthcoming calls and potential collaboration for consortia-building, something very relevant to stakeholders.
- 6 thematic workshops (2 per CoP) / webinars, open to all the members of the Community and where stakeholders may be selected to be speakers and share their expertise.
- Infodays to promote the project and try to get new stakeholders.

4.1.2 Communication

The strategic aspect of communication is very much focused on giving as much visibility as possible to its members and the results achieved as a consequence of the interactions between participants. The content related to stakeholders will therefore be based on their active participation in the community's activities and the results of their interaction with the EIC projects within the scope of the CoP.

The actions planned in terms of communication to keep stakeholders informed about the CoP and its activities are as follows:

- 5 newsletters to with the project supporters and the scientific community while promoting EIC projects and stakeholders.
- 5 project press releases that will promote the project's key developments and outputs to a broader audience.
- 15 success stories delivered in different formats (written stories, video testimonials, podcasts).
- Dedicated social media campaigns.

4.1.3 Action Plan for 2024

The action plan for 2024 incorporates a set of actions that will contribute to the development of the CoP in general and to stakeholders engagement in particular (table 3). The activities may be subject to change (especially those that are adapted to the needs and expectations of each CoP, such as portfolio days and thematic webinars).

Table 3 – Communication activities that target stakeholders

	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December
1st Portfolio Day (3x)								
1st epitching								
1st online thematic webinar								
Newsletter								
Press Release								

5. Conclusions

The purpose of this report was to establish the stakeholders engagement strategy for the CoPs being developed as part of the EIC Communities project. We began by giving an overview of the state of the art in terms of CoP management and stakeholders engagement. The methodological analysis that made it possible to develop this strategy covered the three Community Building Sessions (that were the official starting point for the Industry, Cleantech and Health CoPs). From this analysis, it was possible to identify the following critical success factors:

- the topic that each CoP is going to cover.
- the frequency of events or activities.
- the number of members of each CoP.
- the type of activities to be delivered (stakeholders are very much interested in learning about the European innovation ecosystem and connect with partners for business development purposes).

The stakeholders engagement strategy was based on two main dimensions: events organisation and communication actions. A series of 14 events are planned in which stakeholders will be able to interact with the EIC projects and other stakeholders, or even take on a prominent role as speakers or keynote speakers. In terms of communication, stakeholders will have their participation promoted and, above all, the success stories that result from them, will also be developed.

Finally, it's important to note that this is a living document, in the sense that each CoP will have its own flow in the implementation of activities, as well as different topics to focus on. The principles set out in this report can be further developed in future reports related to CoP management and stakeholder management. Moreover, it is important to note that the results of the strategy and set of actions announced here can only be evaluated as the project develops, but we believe it is a good contribution to the success

of the EIC Communities project and to serve as a basis for deepening the relationship with the stakeholders invited to the CoPs.

The results of the Community Building Sessions will be shared with the EIC PMs and EIC POs to inform them about the needs of the projects.

6. References

Ackoff, R. (1974). *Redesigning the future: A systems approach to societal problems*. Wiley, New York.

Argandoña, A. (1998), The Stakeholder Theory and the Common Good, *Journal of Business Ethics*, No. 17. Available at <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25073938>.

Dunham, L., Freeman R.E., and Liedtka, J. (2006). Enhancing Stakeholder Practice: A Particularized Exploration of Community. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 16(1), January. Available at <https://www.jstor.org/stable/3857725>.

Freeman, R.E. (1984). *Strategic Management: A Stakeholder Approach*. Pitman Publishing Inc., Boston.

Haas, A., Abonneau, D., Borzillo, S. & Guillaume, L. (2020). Afraid of engagement? Towards an understanding of engagement in virtual communities of practice. *Knowledge Management Research & Practice*. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1080/14778238.2020.1745704>.

Parmar, L.; Freeman, R.E.; Harrison, J., *et al.* (2010). Stakeholder Theory: The State of the Art. *Management Faculty Publications*, No. 99. Available at <https://scholarship.richmond.edu/management-faculty-publications/99/>.

Schibi, Ori (2014). *Managing stakeholder expectations for project success. A knowledge integration framework and value focused approach*. J. Ross Publishing, Plantation.

Wenger, Etienne (1998). Communities of Practice: Learning as a Social System. *Systems Thinker*, Vol 9, No. 5, June/July. Available at <https://thesystemsthinker.com/communities-of-practice-learning-as-a-social-system/>.

Wenger, E., McDermott, R. & Snyder, W. (2002). *Cultivating Communities of Practice*. Harvard Business School Press, Boston.

Wenger, E. & Snyder, W. (2020). Communities of Practice: The Organizational Frontier. *Harvard Business Review*, January-February 2020.

Annexes

Participation Guide

EIC COMMUNITIES

Community Building Session
Health CoP

Participation Guide

Funded by
The European Union

European
Innovation
Council

Hello & Welcome!

Community Building Session – Health CoP

Introduction

The Community Building Session you will be participating in is the first event of the EIC Communities project that gathers EIC-supported innovators, EIC Programme Managers and external experts with diverse backgrounds and experiences.

Main Goals:

- Understand expectations and needs of all participants.
- Define main activities and topics to be covered by the CoP.

Health CoP: Topics

- Neurotech
- AI and ML in Medical Imaging

Funded by
the European Union

Community Building Session Format of the event

Zoom & Miro

We'll use Zoom for the online session and Miro as a support platform for interactive group work.

Session Atmosphere

We're aiming for a relaxed session where everyone can share openly about the CoP.

Session Links

Check below for the session links we've shared with you.

Community Building Session Format of the event

Timing

The session is from 10am to 12pm CET, with no scheduled breaks.

Technical Help

For any issues with Zoom or Miro, email Márcia Macieira at marcia.macieira@eura-ag.de.

Funded by
the European Union

Tools

Zoom

- **Zoom for Intro & Conclusion:** We'll start and end the session in Zoom's main room, where everyone will be together.
- **Break-out Rooms for Discussion:** For detailed discussions, we'll use break-out rooms, sorted by CoP topic, to share ideas and comments.
- **Session Recording:** Please note, the session will be recorded.
- **Access Link:** To access the session, follow the provided link: <https://zoom.us/j/98349598149>

Miro

- **Interactive work:** For the online session, we will use Miro, an interactive whiteboard platform.
- **Contributions:** All participants can engage with the content at the same time, contributing through virtual sticky notes, comments, and drawings.
- **Link:** You'll receive an invitation to join the Miro board and can log in with your email address.
- **CoPs:** A template on Miro will guide our discussion on the Community of Practice's structure and growth, where you can post sticky notes with your ideas and feedback.

Miro

1. Select a post-it colour to represent your input throughout the session for easy identification.
2. Add new post-its by copying an existing one or by using the tool menu (fourth icon on the left toolbar).
3. Move post-its by clicking and dragging them to the desired location on the board.
4. The link to the Miro board will be provided during the session for direct access.

Crafting the Future: Key Questions to Shape Our Community of Practices

- 4 main questions will be discussed during the session:
 - What are the expectations of each participant towards the CoP?
 - What can each participant / organisation add to the CoP?
 - What activities would you like to see developed in the CoP?
 - What topics would you like to see covered by the CoP activities?

Agenda

Agenda

COMMUNITY BUILDING SESSION – March 13		
CET TIME		
10:00 – 10:05	Agenda for the day & Welcome words	Main Session
10:05 – 10:35	Individual presentation	Main Session
10:35 – 10:45	EIC Communities: brief presentation	Main Session
10:45 – 11:00	Q&A	Main Session
11:00 – 11:35	Miro exercises	Breakout Rooms
11:35 - 11:40	Live polls	Main Session
11:40 - 12:00	Main conclusions/ Discussion	Main Session
12:00 – 12:05	Closing remarks	Main Session

Guidelines

- Join the session from a quiet space with a webcam, headphones, and microphone. If possible, use two screens during the session: one to work directly on Miro and another to see the colleagues in the Zoom breakout room while discussing.
- Assure that you have a good and stable internet connection.
- Look for an environment that allows you to focus on the proposed activities and speak freely: calm, quiet, and with air circulation.
- Have a notebook with you to register comments, doubts and learnings. In the end of the session, participants will be invited to share some insights and conclusions.
- Have water and snacks at hand, this session is intended to be informal and we won't have a break.
- Always feel comfortable to intervene, make comments or ask questions: communities of practice are all about sharing knowledge and experiences and co-create visions and recommendations, an active communication among participants is key to achieve this.

IC COMMUNITIES

Contacts

APRE as coordinator

- desanti@apre.it
- bonanno@apre.it

EBN as CoP management:

- joanna.abiabdallah@ebn.eu (Industry)
- livia.marcantonio@ebn.eu (Cleantech, Health)
- covadonga.rayon@ebn.eu (Digital)
- raffaele.buompane@ebn.eu (Space)

Funded by
The European Union

Funded by
the European Union

Thank you & see you soon!

Funded by
the European Union